

The missing link in FAIR data policy: data resources

Lucy Poveda¹, Gavin Farrell², Silvio C.E. Tosatto², Monique Zahn-Zabal¹, Patrick Ruch^{1,3}, Julien Gobeil^{1,3}, Robert M. Waterhouse¹, Christophe Dessimoz^{1,4,*}

¹ SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, Lausanne, Switzerland

² Department of Biomedical Sciences, University of Padova, Italy. Via Ugo Bassi 58/B, 35131 Padova, Italy

³ Information Sciences, HES-SO / HEG Geneva, 1227 Carouge, Switzerland

⁴ University of Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland

*Correspondence: christophe.dessimoz@sib.swiss

Abstract

The FAIR principles have reshaped research policy, but their implementation still relies largely on individual researchers—many of whom lack the expertise or support needed to make data truly reusable. Realising FAIR's promise requires sustained investment in the infrastructures that organise, standardise, and curate data: deposition databases and knowledgebases. These data resources are especially critical for AI, which depends on large, high-quality, and consistent data. Landmark advances like AlphaFold and the COVID-19 response illustrate how sustained curation and standardisation in expert resources such as UniProt and the Protein Data Bank have enabled rapid innovation. Yet data resources remain precariously funded, jeopardising long-term sustainability and the expert workforce they require. To support ambitious, data-driven science, funders must align policy and budgets by establishing dedicated mechanisms that allocate a small (e.g., 1%), but strategic and stable share, of research funding to core data infrastructures. This would maximise the value of public investment, strengthen open science and international collaboration, and unlock the full potential of FAIR.

Introduction

Over the past decade, the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016) which provide guidance in making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable have transformed the way research is funded and evaluated. In a paradigm shift, funders now routinely require data management plans, which involves researcher training in FAIR practices and data deposition. The FAIR movement has also led to pronounced behavioural changes among

researchers, while largely overlooking the essential role of infrastructure: the biodata resources — deposition databases and knowledgebases — that turn scattered data sets into readily-available coherent knowledge.

Without infrastructure, FAIR data policy risks becoming a compliance exercise where data might be shared, but remain fragmented, inconsistently annotated, or practically inaccessible. Achieving FAIR at a global scale and reaping its benefits for discovery, artificial intelligence (AI), and innovation depends on infrastructure designed to capture, curate, and connect research data systematically. In life sciences, such infrastructure is referred to as “biodata resources”.

This article argues that investing in biodata resources provides some of the most effective and cost-efficient means of achieving the goal of the FAIR principles. It calls on funders and institutions to provide stable, competitive support for these vital resources such as at a level of at least 1% of research budgets to secure the foundations of FAIR data (Gabella et al. 2018; Mons 2020), accelerate AI-driven discovery, and maximise the impact of public investment in science (Stroe 2021).

FAIR principles in the era of AI

The FAIR principles set the guidelines to ensure data can be readily found, accessed, standardized, and reused by others (Wilkinson et al. 2016). In the era of big data and AI, FAIR is more essential than ever as AI methods require large amounts of data, as their performance is directly dependent on the quality of these data. Furthermore, merely making data available is not enough; it must be understandable to both humans and machines.

AI-driven science needs broad availability of knowledge, not just data (Dessimoz and Thomas 2024). For example, AlphaFold’s revolutionary, AI-based solution to the protein folding problem (Jumper et al. 2021) and recognized by the 2024 Nobel Prize in Chemistry was possible due to decades of work to represent protein structure models in consistent, machine-readable formats. This AI model did not trawl through disparate lab reports, papers, or general purpose data repositories; it learned from the Protein Data Bank (PDB), which contains consistent 3D protein models and rich metadata (Anon 1971; Choudhary et al. 2024), and UniProt, an expertly-curated knowledgebase of protein sequences, functional annotations, and cross-references to other biomolecular databases (UniProt Consortium 2025). Both resources are established and provide high quality data, as evidenced by their recognition as Global Core Biodata Resources (GCBR) (Anon 2023).

These biodata resources continuously provide not only high-quality inputs to AlphaFold, but also a stable framework of identifiers, explicit semantic knowledge in the form of ontologies, and relationships between sequences and structures. These components are essential ingredients for training an AI to be capable of generalizing beyond known examples.

COVID-19 showed how biodata resources turn data into impact

The COVID-19 pandemic offers another striking case study of the role and impact of biodata resources. The rapid publication of the first SARS-CoV-2 genome sequence in January 2020 (Zhu et al. 2020) is rightly celebrated as a triumph of data sharing. But what happened next was critically dependent on long-standing open biodata resources.

The role of biodata infrastructure hosting FAIR data appears evident in retrospect. Researchers were able to rapidly interpret the viral sequence because UniProt, and its specialized resource ViralZone (De Castro et al. 2023), provided expertly curated knowledge on related coronaviruses. This in turn made it possible to comprehensively identify conserved proteins, domains, and functional sites. Within days, highly specific polymerase chain reaction (PCR) diagnostic tests could be designed, not only because the new viral sequence was available, but also because it could immediately be compared to the sequences of other human and animal coronaviruses stored in public databases such as the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) (O’Cathail et al. 2025), ensuring a highly specific test. The structure of the spike protein, critical for vaccine development, was modelled within days as well using SWISS-MODEL (Wu et al. 2020), drawing on public structural data and annotation frameworks. As the virus evolved, real-time tracking of emerging variants was possible thanks to Nextstrain (Hadfield et al. 2018), integrating new genome sequences with global surveillance data.

However, despite the evident contributions of biodata resources to combat a global pandemic, the decades of effort and investment into both curating the data and maintaining the infrastructures went largely unnoticed. These resources represent years of sustained development by the life science data community, and have managed to provide essential, long-term infrastructure on precarious and short-term funded research grants.

FAIR, not bare: the role of deposition databases and knowledgebases

Storing data securely and ensuring its long-term availability for future use is an essential aspect of the research data life cycle. Deposition databases, such as GenBank (Clark et al. 2015) or ENA for nucleotide sequences and the Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive (Iudin et al. 2022) for raw electron microscopy images, ensure that researchers’ original datasets are preserved in a structured way with basic metadata. They make data findable and accessible by assigning persistent unique identifiers and providing search interfaces, thereby making the data reusable by the scientific community. While data and semantically rich metadata are normally domain specific, the need is much broader and generalist repositories such as Zenodo (Anon 2025a) have emerged to support emerging communities.

Knowledgebases such as PomBase (Rutherford et al. 2024) Rhea (Bansal et al. 2021) and Bgee (Bastian et al. 2025), all build on these primary data to produce curated, connected information. According to ELIXIR’s definitions, archival/deposition repositories take in de novo data from scientists, whereas knowledgebases “add substantial value through expert curation, annotation of metadata, sophisticated data processing and data integration” (Durinx

et al. 2017). Knowledgebases build on deposition databases but go significantly further by adding layers of expert curation, semantic integration, and biological interpretation. Their core functions focus on transforming dispersed experimental data and scientific papers into coherent, machine- and human-readable knowledge. In practice, many leading resources even blur the line and do both archive and knowledge building as BioStudies (Sarkans et al. 2018).

While both deposition databases and knowledgebases contribute to the FAIRification of life science data, they play distinct and complementary roles within the data ecosystem (Table 1).

Table 1. Contributions to data FAIRification by the two kinds of infrastructure

<i>Deposition databases</i>	<i>Knowledgebases</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Persistent identifiers:</i> Assigning stable, unique accession numbers (e.g., GenBank/ENA accession numbers for sequences, PDB identifiers for experimental protein structures) or in few cases DOIs as in ModelArchive (Tauriello et al. 2025), making data reliably findable and citable. ● <i>Basic quality control:</i> Enforcing minimum metadata requirements and standard file formats at the point of submission, ensuring deposited data meet community-agreed standards of completeness and structure. ● <i>Standardization of formats:</i> Mandating common syntactic and semantic standards (e.g., FASTA, VCF, mmCIF, JATS), thus facilitating data parsing and exchange. ● <i>Long-term preservation:</i> Providing technical 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Expert curation & quality control:</i> Evaluating, annotating, and integrating evidence from multiple sources (often including literature), ensuring accuracy, consistency, and biological relevance far beyond minimal deposition standards. ● <i>Semantic standardization & ontologies:</i> Co-developing and applying controlled vocabularies and community ontologies (e.g., Gene Ontology, Disease Ontology) to describe biological concepts, enabling interoperability not just at the data format level, but at the semantic level. ● <i>Cross-referencing & integration:</i> Linking diverse data types (genes, proteins, pathways, phenotypes, literature) and identifiers across databases, creating rich knowledge graphs that reflect biological relationships. ● <i>Aggregation & synthesis:</i> Combining evidence across species, experiments, and data types, providing consensus views or generalized knowledge (e.g., GO annotations summarizing gene functions across organisms).

-
- infrastructure, ensuring the accessibility of data over time.
- *Discoverability tools*: Providing search interfaces and APIs, allowing users/machines to locate and retrieve relevant datasets.
 - *Search and analysis tools*: Providing user-friendly interfaces, programmatic access, and visualizations, facilitating discovery and reuse of curated knowledge.
 - *Community training & support*: Offering detailed documentation, tutorials, and help desks guiding users in data deposition, access, and reuse, thereby fostering best practices across the research community.

Curation and curation-support infrastructure

Curation is an expert driven task, which requires skilled professionals covering all aspects of life sciences. In addition to a specialized workforce, the effort is based on a complex ecosystem. It includes basic IT services for storage and compute, as well specialized services to help curators performing their knowledge extraction tasks. Further, curation is directly dependent on the availability of publications, whose access has been greatly enhanced thanks to Open Access libraries such as EuropePMC (Europe PMC Consortium 2015) or SIBiLS / BiodiversityPMC (Europe PMC Consortium 2015; Gobeill et al. 2020). Curated databases were also pioneers in exploring how AI-driven search engines - today's Retrieval Augmented Generation - can support their curation workflows (Leitner et al. 2008). Today, these databases are evolving towards delivering accurate data description workflows (Gobeill et al. 2018) and schemas, supported with semantically unambiguous descriptors (e.g., accession numbers, ontological concepts (Gaudet and Dessimoz 2017), to deliver a high-density data net tailored to directly drive AI developments.

Knowledgebases as critical enablers of AI breakthroughs

Life science knowledgebases deserve, indeed, special attention in the context of AI developments. By transcending individual experiments, they create a consensus view of biology and make it available through machine-readable formats and interfaces. This integrated, consistent, and quality-controlled layer of distilled knowledge is a layer above the raw data and exactly what AI algorithms need for effective training and testing. An AI trying to reason about gene function or disease mechanisms benefits enormously from the existence of a curated knowledge graph, rather than having to infer connections from scattered experimental datasets. Building such knowledge representations through synthesis and consensus has become an increasingly important role in science, filled by expert biocurators in projects like Gene Ontology and UniProt. The result is knowledgebases that make the latest knowledge broadly usable beyond the original subfield and available for

computational exploitation (Dessimoz and Thomas 2024). In essence, knowledgebases convert the deluge of specialized data into an organized, interoperable knowledge network, paving the road for AI-driven discoveries.

AI and knowledgebases are being used in a range of applications. PomBase (Rutherford et al. 2024) integrates information about *Schizosaccharomyces pombe* (fission yeast) through expert literature curation such as genome sequences, gene functions and mutant phenotypes, thus serving as a reference for a study applying phenomics and machine-learning approaches (Rodríguez-López et al. 2023). The team providing Rhea (Bansal et al. 2021), an expert-curated knowledgebase of chemical and transport reactions of biological interest, also generated EnzChemRED (Enzyme Chemistry Relation Extraction Dataset), a new training and benchmarking dataset to support the development of Natural Language Processing (NLP) methods (Gu et al. 2022; Lai et al. 2024). Bgee takes gene expression data (from RNA-seq, in situ hybridization, etc.) from many different species and conditions, and curates them into a consistent baseline of where genes are expressed, using anatomy ontologies and rigorous quality checks. They are currently developing a pilot implementation of annotation of single-cell RNA-Seq data guided by AI.

The complementary roles of researchers and biodata resources

Current efforts to achieve FAIR principles heavily emphasize the role of individual researchers. These should undergo data management training, write data management plans, structure and annotate data using appropriate standards before submission to data repositories. But there are limits to a purely researcher-centric approach in completing these important tasks. Expecting every lab to become expert in metadata standards, ontologies, and long-term data curation is inefficient and unrealistic. Researchers are trained to innovate at the frontier of science; asking them to also master data archiving and interoperability standards for each dataset diverts their time and efforts, as well as often resulting in suboptimal outcomes. For instance, inconsistent metadata or under-annotated datasets, while technically “available,” are hard to reuse.

Centralized resources can achieve these aspects of FAIRification more efficiently. Biodata resource staff specialize in data curation and interoperability; they can perform these tasks at scale, with higher expertise and automation level, while still maintaining quality requirements. When deposition databases enforce standard formats and metadata upon submission, they automatically improve consistency and findability. Knowledgebase curators, in turn, devote focused effort to refining and linking data, a job that would be prohibitively laborious if every lab attempted to do so in isolation. Notably, this approach is often more cost-effective: even for emerging and complex data types, which typically require labour-intensive curation by experts, the costs at a centralized resource are only a small fraction of the cost of generating the data in the first place, yet increase the data value many-fold (Dessimoz and Thomas 2024).

Funding challenges and the case for sustained investment

Even as biodata resources become more critical to science and innovation, many of them face precarious funding. Millions of life scientists worldwide rely on bioinformatics databases, especially high-value curated knowledgebases, yet most of these resources lack secured funding and depend on short-term grants that do not match their long-term mission (Anderson and Global Life Science Data Resources Working Group 2017). Too often, these resources are forced to compete as though they were conventional research projects, rather than as essential infrastructure. This misalignment can lead to chronic underfunding, with funding gaps leading to the loss of highly specialised personnel. Unlike individual research projects, which can sometimes be paused or delayed with limited wider consequences, a biodata resource underpins an entire network of dependent users, services, and tools. Interruptions in their operation reverberate widely, making their stability not just desirable but essential.

The Global Biodata Coalition's establishment of a list of Global Core Biodata Resources (GCBRs) is a direct response to these concerns. GCBRs are those databases considered "of fundamental importance to the wider life-science community... and the long-term preservation of biological data," whose loss would have "a highly detrimental impact on the global research endeavour". Still, the efforts of the Global Biodata Coalition have yet to result in new funding instruments for resources or budget increases in the existing ones. On the contrary, despite continued increase of usage and an embrace of FAIR principles by funders, the amount of funding available for biodata resources has tended to diminish in the last decade. The Wellcome Trust has discontinued competitive biodata resource funding, and funding through national instruments (notably NIH, BBSRC or Swiss Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation) has not kept up with inflation, let alone with the usage growth. As a result, several Global Core Biodata Resources have lost major funding sources in recent years.

This state of affairs is all the more paradoxical considering that the level of funding required to sustain the activity of the most impactful biodata resources would be surprisingly affordable. Gabella et al (2018) outlined an "Infrastructure Model" of funding, wherein agencies set aside a fixed portion of grant budgets to fund core data resources in a stable, competitive way. Their estimates suggest that less than 1% of life science research funding would suffice to cover the worldwide costs of core data resources for knowledgebases and deposition archives. This is a remarkably small fraction to ensure that the most important data and knowledge produced can be properly preserved and made FAIR. Considering the outsized impact these resources have, both in terms of making sure that past investments in research are not lost and accelerating the production of new knowledge, supporting them may be one of the highest returns on investment in research available today.

Aligning responsibilities, recognition, and incentives

Achieving and sustaining FAIR data is a shared responsibility. Researchers who generate data have a responsibility to organize and deposit their data in appropriate repositories with the appropriate metadata. Data resource teams (curators, software engineers, data scientists, data stewards) take on the responsibility of maintaining and enhancing these data for the community. Funders and research institutions, in turn, carry the responsibility of enabling this ecosystem through competitive funding and monitoring, policy, and recognition.

Such division of labour requires policy changes and cultural shifts in how we evaluate and reward contributions in science. Maintaining a widely-used database or curating an ontology can be just as vital to scientific progress as authoring a high-profile paper, yet traditional academic reward systems often undervalue such contributions. Here, the emerging principles of initiatives like CoARA (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment) (Anon 2025b) are highly pertinent. CoARA calls for a broad recognition of the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research and explicitly seeks to integrate the recognition of contributions to open science—including data sharing and infrastructure—in research assessment.

Crucially, a more holistic view of scientific contributions means funders recognising biodata resources not as “burden” (Imker 2020) or an expenditure “to the detriment of new research” (Johnson and Bourne 2023), but as core scholarly activities integral to fulfilling their mission. In Europe, initiatives like EOSC have recognised the critical importance of issues such as defining trustworthy repositories, ensuring long-term data preservation, establishing a transdisciplinary expert curation network, and improving data discoverability. Currently, these topics are addressed within short-term projects, typically lasting only three to four years, such as FIDELIS, EOSC EDEN (Anon 2025c), and EOSC Data Commons (Anon 2025d). Importantly, these projects do not fund the maintenance of the underlying deposition databases and knowledgebases they depend on; rather, they build upon existing resources. To ensure continuity, sustainability, and real impact, there is an urgent need for a dedicated and long-term funding instrument in Europe. Dedicated funding instruments — guided by the same principles of excellence, impact, and competitiveness that apply to research grants, but tailored to the specific role of resources (e.g. Gabella et al. 2022) — would provide both the clear signalling and sustained investment needed to make FAIR a reality in practice. This, in turn, would foster stronger collaboration between researchers and data curators and ensure that critical knowledgebases can keep pace with the growing demands placed upon them.

Securing FAIR’s missing link and science’s return on investment

In summary, FAIR data is the fuel driving modern life science research and innovation (Lauer et al. 2021), and its importance is only amplified by the rise of AI and data-driven discovery. While we rightly encourage individual researchers to manage and share their data through the FAIR movement, we must find a way to support the critical role of data resources, the

deposition databases and knowledgebases that actually make data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable in practice. These resources perform the heavy lifting of data standardization, integration, and preservation and turn isolated experimental results into collective scientific knowledge. They exemplify how democratizing data increases its value: once data is integrated into a curated knowledgebase, they can serve the entire community and spark new discoveries well beyond the original lab's research intentions and individual subfields. They make it possible to turn a newly sequenced virus genome into highly accurate PCR tests within days, vaccines within months, and a flood of fragmented sequences into real-time global surveillance to address global pandemics and enable science-based policies.

The return on investment in such resources is extraordinarily high (Beagrie and Houghton 2021), yet their funding and recognition has lagged behind their impact. It is time for funders and institutions to treat biodata resources as essential infrastructure, despite their digital nature, as they are equally if not more important than physical laboratories and instrumentation. We strongly encourage them to be recognised, supported and financed accordingly. Dedicating in the order of 1% of research funding to core data resources would ensure that the outputs of the other 99% are properly conserved and made maximally useful. Moreover, embracing a holistic view of scientific contribution in line with CoARA will foster an environment where data sharing and curation are rewarded, not neglected.

In the quest for effective cures, sustainable agriculture, environmental solutions, and fundamental insights into life, data resources are our knowledge vaults and launchpads. Strengthening these resources is a direct investment in the future of FAIR, open, and AI-enabled science – an investment our research ecosystem cannot afford to shortchange.

Acknowledgements

This study received funding from ELIXIR: the research infrastructure for life-science data. In addition, we acknowledge SNSF grant #205085 to C.D.

References

- Anderson WP, Global Life Science Data Resources Working Group. 2017. Data management: A global coalition to sustain core data. *Nature* [Internet] 543:179. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/543179a>
- Anon. 1971. Crystallography: Protein Data Bank. *Nat. New Biol.* [Internet] 233:223–223. Available from: <https://www.nature.com/articles/newbio233223b0>
- Anon. 2023. List of Current Global Core Biodata Resources. *Global Biodata Coalition* [Internet]. Available from: <https://globalbiodata.org/what-we-do/global-core-biodata-resources/list-of-current-global-core-biodata-resources/>

- Anon. 2025a. Zenodo. Available from: <https://zenodo.org>
- Anon. 2025b. The Agreement – CoARA. Available from: <https://coara.eu/agreement/the-agreement-full-text/>
- Anon. 2025c. Available from: <https://eden-fidelis.eu>
- Anon. 2025d. Homepage. *EOSC Data Commons* [Internet]. Available from: <https://www.eosc-data-commons.eu>
- Bansal P, Morgat A, Axelsen KB, Muthukrishnan V, Coudert E, Aimo L, Hyka-Nouspikel N, Gasteiger E, Kerhornou A, Neto TB, et al. 2021. Rhea, the reaction knowledgebase in 2022. *Nucleic Acids Res* [Internet] 50:D693–D700. Available from: <https://academic.oup.com/nar/article-pdf/50/D1/D693/42058388/gkab1016.pdf>
- Bastian FB, Cammarata AB, Carsanaro S, Detering H, Huang W-T, Joye S, Niknejad A, Nyamari M, Mendes de Farias T, Moretti S, et al. 2025. Bgee in 2024: focus on curated single-cell RNA-seq datasets, and query tools. *Nucleic Acids Res.* [Internet] 53:D878–D885. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae1118>
- Beagrie N, Houghton J. 2021. Data-driven discovery: The value and impact of EMBL-EBI managed data resources. Available from: <https://www.embl.org/documents/document/embl-ebi-impact-report-2021/>
- Choudhary P, Feng Z, Berrisford J, Chao H, Ikegawa Y, Peisach E, Piehl DW, Smith J, Tanweer A, Varadi M, et al. 2024. PDB NextGen Archive: centralizing access to integrated annotations and enriched structural information by the Worldwide Protein Data Bank. *Database (Oxford)* [Internet] 2024. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/database/baae041>
- Clark K, Karsch-Mizrachi I, Lipman DJ, Ostell J, Sayers EW. 2015. GenBank. *Nucleic Acids Res* [Internet] 44:D67–D72. Available from: <https://academic.oup.com/nar/article-pdf/44/D1/D67/9483609/gkv1276.pdf>
- De Castro E, Hulo C, Masson P, Auchincloss A, Bridge A, Le Mercier P. 2023. ViralZone 2024 provides higher-resolution images and advanced virus-specific resources. *Nucleic Acids Res* [Internet] 52:D817–D821. Available from: <https://academic.oup.com/nar/article-pdf/52/D1/D817/55042344/gkad946.pdf>
- Dessimoz C, Thomas PD. 2024. AI and the democratization of knowledge. *Sci. Data* [Internet] 11:268. Available from: https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=en&citation_for_view=QI nd7HoAAAAJ:654Jc7Ppz2kC
- Durinx C, McEntyre J, Appel R, Apweiler R, Barlow M, Blomberg N, Cook C, Gasteiger E, Kim J-H, Lopez R, et al. 2017. Identifying ELIXIR Core Data Resources. *F1000Res.* [Internet] 5:2422. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.9656.2>
- Europe PMC Consortium. 2015. Europe PMC: a full-text literature database for the life sciences and platform for innovation. *Nucleic Acids Res* [Internet] 43:D1042–D1048. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/nar/gku1061>
- Gabella C, Durinx C, Appel R. 2018. Funding knowledgebases: Towards a sustainable funding model for the UniProt use case. *F1000Res.* [Internet] 6:2051. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.12989.2>

- Gabella C, Duvaud S, Durinx C. 2022. Managing the life cycle of a portfolio of open data resources at the SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics. *Brief. Bioinform.* [Internet] 23. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbab478>
- Gaudet P, Dessimoz C. 2017. Gene Ontology: Pitfalls, Biases, and Remedies. *Methods Mol Biol* [Internet] 1446:189–205. Available from: http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-3743-1_14
- Gobeill J, Caucheteur D, Michel P-A, Mottin L, Pasche E, Ruch P. 2020. SIB Literature Services: RESTful customizable search engines in biomedical literature, enriched with automatically mapped biomedical concepts. *Nucleic Acids Res* [Internet] 48:W12–W16. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaa328>
- Gobeill J, Gaudet P, Dopp D, Morrone A, Kahanda I, Hsu Y-Y, Wei C-H, Lu Z, Ruch P. 2018. Overview of the BioCreative VI text-mining services for Kinome Curation Track. *Database (Oxford)* [Internet] 2018. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/database/bay104>
- Gu Y, Tinn R, Cheng H, Lucas M, Usuyama N, Liu X, Naumann T, Gao J, Poon H. 2022. Domain-specific language model pretraining for biomedical natural language processing. *ACM Trans. Comput. Healthc.* [Internet] 3:1–23. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3458754>
- Hadfield J, Megill C, Bell SM, Huddleston J, Potter B, Callender C, Sagulenko P, Bedford T, Neher RA. 2018. Nextstrain: real-time tracking of pathogen evolution. *Bioinformatics* [Internet] 34:4121–4123. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty407>
- Imker HJ. 2020. Who bears the burden of long-lived molecular biology databases? *Data Sci. J.* [Internet] 19:8. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-008>
- Iudin A, Korir PK, Somasundharam S, Weyand S, Cattavittello C, Fonseca N, Salih O, Kleywegt GJ, Patwardhan A. 2022. EMPIAR: the Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive. *Nucleic Acids Res* [Internet] 51:D1503–D1511. Available from: <https://academic.oup.com/nar/article-pdf/51/D1/D1503/49645431/gkac1062.pdf>
- Johnson TR, Bourne PE. 2023. The biological data sustainability paradox. *arXiv [q-bio.OT]* [Internet]. Available from: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2311.05668>
- Jumper J, Evans R, Pritzel A, Green T, Figurnov M, Ronneberger O, Tunyasuvunakool K, Bates R, Žídek A, Potapenko A, et al. 2021. Highly accurate protein structure prediction with AlphaFold. *Nature* [Internet] 596:583–589. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03819-2>
- Lai P-T, Coudert E, Aimo L, Axelsen K, Breuza L, de Castro E, Feuermann M, Morgat A, Pourcel L, Pedruzzi I, et al. 2024. EnzChemRED, a rich enzyme chemistry relation extraction dataset. *Scientific Data* [Internet] 11:1–19. Available from: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-024-03835-7>
- Lauer KB, Smith A, Blomberg N, Sitjà XP, Talbot-Cooper C, Rothe H, Conde DS. 2021. Open data: A driving force for innovation in the life sciences. *F1000Research* [Internet] 10:828. Available from: <https://f1000research.com/documents/10-828/pdf>
- Leitner F, Krallinger M, Rodriguez-Penagos C, Hakenberg J, Plake C, Kuo C-J, Hsu C-N, Tsai RT-H, Hung H-C, Lau WW, et al. 2008. Introducing meta-services for biomedical information extraction. *Genome Biology* [Internet] 9:1–11. Available from: <https://genomebiology.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/gb-2008-9-s2-s6>

- Mons B. 2020. Invest 5% of research funds in ensuring data are reusable. *Nature Publishing Group UK* [Internet]. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-00505-7>
- O’Cathail C, Ahamed A, Burgin J, Cummins C, Devaraj R, Gueye K, Gupta D, Gupta V, Haseeb M, Ihsan M, et al. 2025. The European Nucleotide Archive in 2024. *Nucleic Acids Res.* [Internet] 53:D49–D55. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae975>
- Rodríguez-López M, Bordin N, Lees J, Scholes H, Hassan S, Saintain Q, Kamrad S, Orengo C, Bähler J. 2023. Broad functional profiling of fission yeast proteins using phenomics and machine learning. Available from: <https://elifesciences.org/articles/88229>
- Rutherford KM, Lera-Ramírez M, Wood V. 2024. PomBase: a Global Core Biodata Resource-growth, collaboration, and sustainability. *Genetics* [Internet] 227. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/genetics/iyae007>
- Sarkans U, Gostev M, Athar A, Behranghi E, Melnichuk O, Ali A, Minguet J, Rada JC, Snow C, Tikhonov A, et al. 2018. The BioStudies database-one stop shop for all data supporting a life sciences study. *Nucleic Acids Res.* [Internet] 46:D1266–D1270. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkx965>
- Stroe O. 2021. Open data on the rise: the value of EMBL-EBI data resources. *EMBL-EBI News* [Internet]. Available from: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/about/news/announcements/value-and-impact-embledi-2021/>
- Tauriello G, Waterhouse AM, Haas J, Behringer D, Bienert S, Garello T, Schwede T. 2025. ModelArchive: A deposition database for computational macromolecular structural models. *J. Mol. Biol.* [Internet]:168996. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jmb.2025.168996>
- UniProt Consortium. 2025. UniProt: The universal protein knowledgebase in 2025. *Nucleic Acids Res.* [Internet] 53:D609–D617. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae1010>
- Wilkinson MD, Dumontier M, Aalbersberg IJJ, Appleton G, Axton M, Baak A, Blomberg N, Boiten J-W, da Silva Santos LB, Bourne PE, et al. 2016. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* [Internet] 3:160018. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- Wu F, Zhao S, Yu B, Chen Y-M, Wang W, Song Z-G, Hu Y, Tao Z-W, Tian J-H, Pei Y-Y, et al. 2020. A new coronavirus associated with human respiratory disease in China. *Nature* [Internet] 579:265–269. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2008-3>
- Zhu N, Zhang D, Wang W, Li X, Yang B, Song J, Zhao X, Huang B, Shi W, Lu R, et al. 2020. A Novel Coronavirus from Patients with Pneumonia in China, 2019. *New England Journal of Medicine* [Internet]. Available from: <https://www.nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMoa2001017>